

Role and importance of EIP-AGRI Operational Group members in Horizon Europe Multi-Actor projects

Focus Group N° 3, 7 April 2025, 10:00-12:15 CET

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This document presents the authors' perspective and not the
position of the European Commission or its services.

Series of PREMIERE Focus Groups

- ...discuss Multi-Actor specifics for policy recommendations, which help to improve the 'enabling environment' for interactive innovation.
- ... is highly relevant because many more Horizon Europe (HE) Call Topics will require the application of the Multi-Actor Approach (MAA).
- ... are co-created by the PREMIERE team and its DG-AGRI Policy Officers supported by REA Project Officers

PREMIERE Focus Groups

1. Programming the Multi-Actor Approach (6/2024)
2. Evaluation of the MAA (1/2025)
3. OGS-go-Horizon (4/2025)
4. Seed funding for Horizon newcomers (?)
5. MAA in the wider context of Open Science, Citizen, civil society and user engagement (and RRI - Responsible Research & Innovation) (?)
6. (?)

PREMIERE Focus Group – Introduction

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Time	Title	Speakers/Facilitators
10:00 – 10:10	Welcome Icebreaker (Menti) Introduction	Susanne von Münchhausen and Albert Escolà (DARPA)
10:10 – 10:30	Overview of the survey outputs	Albert Escolà and Lluc Tost
10:30 – 10:45	Questions & Comments	All, Hanna Tamsalu
10:45	Break (10 minutes)	
10:55 – 11:30	Group discussion in Breakout rooms	Hanna Tamsalu (METK), Shane Conway (Galway University), Susanne von Münchhausen (HNEE), Jordi Pietx (HCC), Vesna Miličić (CCIS – CAFE)
11:30 – 12:05	Discussion of the groups' recommendations	All, Hanna Tamsalu
12:05 – 12:15	Reflection (Menti)	Albert Escolà
	Next steps	Susanne von Münchhausen

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Mentimeter

WELCOME to our PREMIERE Focus Group

PREMIERE Focus Group – Introduction

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PREMIERE – Preparing Multi-Actor Projects in a Co-creative Way

PREMIERE aims to

- Contribute to more effective programming and implementation of the multi-actor approach (MAA), and
- provide support to those preparing multi-actor proposals.

PREMIERE Focus Group – Introduction

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About PREMIERE

Type: Coordination and Support Action (CSA)
Multi-Actor (MA) project

Partners: 15 diverse organisations from
across Europe,
based in 12 EU Member States

Coordinator: Eberswalde University (HNEE)

Duration: January 2023 – December 2027

Budget: around 5 million Euro

Social media: @premiere_eu

Homepage: www.premiere-multiactor.eu

PREMIERE material and services

About this Focus Group

We aim to

- Assess the role and importance of representatives EIP-AGRI Operational Groups (OG) in HE multi-actor projects and proposals
- Reach a good understanding of the associated challenges for MA project leaders and participating practice/OG partners
- Translate the results into policy briefs for policymakers at regional, national and EU levels
- Feed into the preparation of the next EU R&I programmes and future CAP

PREMIERE Focus Group – Introduction

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Why do we focus on ‚OGs go HE‘?

Results from PREMIERE's FG 1 on the MAA:

- HE proposals are mainly coordinated by universities -> Access to practitioners is challenging
- Encourage OG involvement because they have local networks and their activities are needs-driven
- OGs need targeted support to develop their understanding and competencies

PREMIERE Focus Group – Introduction

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And: Policy Officers want to better understand

- ... the current situation of OGs in MA projects.
- ... the (potential) benefits of OGs in HE.
- ... the main challenges of OG in HE.
- ... how they can improve programming and administration for OG involvement in HE.
- ... how to increase in number of OG participants and their practice-oriented perspectives in HE projects.

PREMIERE Focus Group – Introduction

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Preparation for this 3rd Focus Group

PREMIERE Focus Group – Introduction

Survey Outcomes:

Responses for the Focus Group 'Operational Groups go Horizon'

PREMIERE Focus Group #3, online, 7th April 2025

Albert Escolà i Soles, Lluc Tost i Lopez, Hanna
Tamsalu, Susanne v. Münchhausen

Overview

- 1) Introduction to the survey (stream A and B)
- 2) Survey results of OG-related entries (A)
- 3) Survey results of HE Multi-Actor project - related entries (B)
- 4) Questions answered by (A) and (B)

1) Introduction to the survey

- ▶ Online survey with two streams: (A) for participants of Operational Group (OG) projects, and (B) for those experienced in Horizon Europe (HE) Multi-Actor projects.
- ▶ In total, 124 entries; thereof 58 from OG and 66 from HE experts

Results from Survey 'OG go Horizon' from Premiere HE - March 2025

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2) Survey results of OG-related entries (A)

Are you currently, or were you partner of an EIP-AGRI Operational Groups (OGs)?

Results from Survey 'OG go Horizon' from Premiere HE - March 2025

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In how many EIP-AGRI OGs have you been involved?

Results from Survey 'OG go Horizon' from Premiere HE - March 2025

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How would you rate your experience with the most recent EIP-AGRI OG?

Results from Survey 'OG go Horizon' from Premiere HE - March 2025

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How would you characterize your most recent or ongoing OG project?

Results from Survey 'OG go Horizon' from Premiere HE - March 2025

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What has been the primary benefit of participating in your last EIP-AGRI OGs?

Results from Survey 'OG go Horizon' from Premiere HE - March 2025

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What have we learned from the OG experts answering the survey so far?

- ▶ Nearly half of the entries come from OG members, which is great.
- ▶ Two-thirds of the OG members participated in more than one OG project. The OG-related answers come from 'OG experts'.
- ▶ Many had very good experiences with OG projects!
- ▶ Most OGs were classified as 'technical development projects' with medium and low TRL (Technology Readiness Levels). These teams are suitable for Research and Innovation (RIA) project participation. Very few OG projects have high TRL.

Results from Survey 'OG go Horizon' from Premiere HE - March 2025

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What challenges have you encountered while participating in EIP-AGRI OGs?

Results from Survey 'OG go Horizon' from Premiere HE - March 2025

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What else did we see in the OG-related survey?

- ▶ Apart from technical developments, OG members benefited from new products or methods and from sharing knowledge
- ▶ Most relevant challenges for the OGs:
 - 1) Administrative burden and
 - 2) Limited funding to fulfil the work
- ▶ Access to technical and other resources was ranked lower for the OG members.

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Survey results for OG members in Horizon projects

Have you participated in a Horizon 2020 or Horizon Europe Multi-Actor project?

If yes, has this EU project involved any EIP-AGRI OG members?

Results from Survey 'OG go Horizon' from Premiere HE - March 2025

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... OG-related survey results

- ▶ Around half of the OG experts also participated in Horizon MA **projects**, but only 25% of these EU projects involved OG members.
- ▶ Most OG experts voted for
 - ▶ OG members to be 'Full partners' when joining a Horizon project proposal, followed by acting as stakeholders.
 - ▶ 'More funding needed' for OG members to be more effective in their role as Horizon project participants.
 - ▶ Followed by 'more networking opportunities' needed for OG members and 'Training in financial administration'

Results from Survey 'OG go Horizon' from Premiere HE - March 2025

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Comments of OG members

▶ OG's Potential & Bridging the Gap with HE

- ▶ "We believe that Operational Groups (OGs) have significant potential to create a strong impact on EU Horizon projects. Efforts should be made to bridge the gap between the two programs.
The pilot tests carried out in our OGs should be better disseminated and supported in connection with HE."

▶ Excessive Bureaucracy as a Systemic Barrier

- ▶ "One of the main obstacles is excessive bureaucracy and the lack of flexibility in allocating resources to the real needs of the projects."

Results from Survey 'OG go Horizon' from Premiere HE - March 2025

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Comments of OG members

► Legal, Data & IP Challenges Overlooked in Multi-Actor Projects

- "One aspect that is not well addressed in the multi-actor approach is dealing with open data, GDPR, and intellectual and industrial property rights... There is a lack of guidance on these issues when preparing proposals and during project implementation."

► Language Barrier Limiting Participation

- "For EU-level projects, the English language often becomes a barrier. This means that farmers who could contribute valuable knowledge and ideas may stay away, leading to missed opportunities for innovation and experience-sharing."

Results from Survey 'OG go Horizon' from Premiere HE - March 2025

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Results from Survey 'OG go Horizon' from Premiere HE - March 2025

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Has your organization participated in a project with mandatory application of the Multi-Actor Approach (MAA)?

Results from Survey 'OG go Horizon' from Premiere HE - March 2025

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What was your role in the Multi-Actor project(s)?

Results from Survey 'OG go Horizon' from Premiere HE - March 2025

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What have been the three most important benefits of participating in Horizon Europe projects?

Results from Survey 'OG go Horizon' from Premiere HE - March 2025

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Insights from the survey of Horizon expert

- ▶ Most Horizon experts participated in a MA project; however a substantial number of experts did not know if they were involved in a project with a mandatory application of the MAA – interesting.
- ▶ Many participants experienced different roles in various projects
- ▶ For Horizon experts 'Research & Innovation' and 'Access to funding' are the main benefits when joining EU projects. Networking opportunities are also relevant
- ▶ 'New products and methods' are less relevant, which is different to the answers from those benefiting from OG projects

Results from Survey 'OG go Horizon' from Premiere HE - March 2025

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If your organization has participated in a HE project, did the project involve any EIP-AGRI OG actors?

Results from Survey 'OG go Horizon' from Premiere HE - March 2025

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If the project involved OG members, Were you directly involved in integrating them into the project?

Results from Survey 'OG go Horizon' from Premiere HE - March 2025

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Which good practices did you as HE expert observe in successful OGs?

Results from Survey 'OG go Horizon' from Premiere HE - March 2025

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Experiences of Horizon project members with OGs

- ▶ The survey participants represented very few HE projects involving OG members
- ▶ 'Facilitation and stakeholder involvement' is highlighted as a good practice of OGs
- ▶ HE experts also value the access to 'local expertise' and to 'testing/piloting'

Results from Survey 'OG go Horizon' from Premiere HE - March 2025

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Comments of the Horizon experts

► Structural Barriers & Need for Systemic Alignment

- "Frequently, the OGs have a different temporal development compared to HE projects, which makes it complicated to work with them. OGs have a 'strict' work plan with financial constraints posed by the funding authority (e.g., obligation of spending 60% of budget for staff, which sometimes is not necessary). This makes it difficult for them (and the HE project) to widen or introduce new common activities."

► OG Visibility & Legal Identity

- "EIP-AGRI OGs should be recognisable as an entity, or at least a legal representative must be appointed in order to facilitate their collaboration with Horizon projects. For example, there is no legal representative, who can sign the non-disclosure agreements. But they are crucial for the dissemination of innovations."

Results from Survey 'OG go Horizon' from Premiere HE - March 2025

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Comments of the HE experts

► Reducing Bureaucracy & Contextual Adaptation

- Reduce bureaucracy
- Evaluate the RESULTS of projects 2 and 5 years later
- Acknowledge that the Mediterranean exists and is unlike any other countries in the EU
- Prioritize reality over virtuality in project selection
- Facilitate personnel contracts between countries
- Reject all projects that include terms like "sustainability, AI, words ending in 'omics,' efficiency..." without proper context in their wording
- value sobriety in solutions, as well as common sense and empathy in their application.

► Funding Continuity & Long-Term Strategy

- "EIP-Agri OGs that have no funding vanish quickly. In a project-work-based world, the projects die once the final report is submitted. The EC needs a long-term strategy for EIP-agri OGs."

Results from Survey 'OG go Horizon' from Premiere HE - March 2025

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How can EIP-AGRI OG best contribute to Horizon Europe projects?

Results from Survey 'OG go Horizon' from Premiere HE - March 2025

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What barriers do you see in integrating OG members into HE project consortia?

Results from Survey 'OG go Horizon' from Premiere HE - March 2025

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To conclude the overview of survey results

- ▶ When OGs are involved in HE projects, the HE experts highlight the 'Insights to real-world challenges' and 'OGs support dissemination'.
- ▶ OG members highlight their role
 - as facilitators between research and practice, and
 - as key implementation partner
- ▶ Main barriers for OGs joining Horizon:
 - OG members fear complex administration;
 - HE experts highlight the lack of information about Horizon among OG members.

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12:05 – 12:15	Questions & Comments Reflection (Menti)	Albert Escolà
	Next steps	Susanne von Münchhausen

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Five breakout groups

- 1. Opening the Door to Horizon Europe: Inclusion and Engagement for OG members** –
Shane Conway (University of Galway) and Lluc Tost (DARPA)
- 2. Resources, Skills, Capacities of OG members to engage in Horizon MA projects** –
Hanna Tamsalu and Konstantin Mihhejev (METK)
- 3. Role of OG members in Horizon Project** – Susanne von Münchhausen (HNEE) and Pierre Rochepeau (ARVALIS)
- 4. Funding options for OG participation in Horizon Europe** –
Jordi Pietx and Mark Redman (HCC)
- 5. Finding and aligning: How can OG members fit and be aligned in the HE Call Topics?** – Vesna Milicic and Zala Plateis (CCIS-CAFE)

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Next steps of this 3rd Focus Group

FG workshop

Session:

- 15 to 20 participants
- Duration: 2h
- Prepared material
- Thorough harvesting from the discussions

07/04/2025

Post-meeting tasks

- Focus Group report
- Validation/feedback
- Presentation of results on 16 May 2025, BxIs and other events
- Policy brief

April-May/2025

PREMIERE Focus Group – Introduction

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